

Web-Based Application for the Loan Servicing of Maritime Employees Multi-Purpose Cooperative

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Abstract

This study aimed to produce a loan servicing application for Maritime Employees Multi-Purpose Cooperative (MEMPCO). Specifically, this study aimed to meet the following objectives: 1) develop a database using a free relational database management system; 2) build a web-based application for the manager and members; 3) produce an online application with the following features: accessing the system with appropriate credentials; viewing and updating of select member information; applying, granting, and viewing of loans; posting and viewing of payments; and generating the billing statement; and 4) describe the features of the developed application based on the selected characteristics defined in the ISO 9126-1 software quality model. This study utilized both the Scrum methodology and descriptive-evaluative design. XAMPP that is bundled with MySQL and PHP, Notepad++, HTML, JavaScript, and CSS were the tools and languages used in the development. The produced application was designed to cater to two types of users—manager and member. On one hand, a member of the said cooperative is allowed to apply loan via the developed application, update certain information, and view pertinent data. On the other hand, the manager will have the maximum access to the system. The produced web-based application for MEMPCO is a more effective and efficient solution to complete loan servicing transactions. Among others, the use of the said application ensures accuracy in the computation of amortization and loan balance. The computation produces accurate results through a more convenient and faster way compared to the existing system.

Keywords: loan servicing, ISO 9126, MySQL, PHP, software development

Introduction

Information and communications technology (ICT) has brought people across lands closer to each other. Nowadays, people of different ages, people of various nationalities, and people of different kinds enjoy the benefits of online social networking, gaming, and business transactions. Despite of the wonders of technology on networking, computing, and information processing, still, there are a numbers of systems done manually or perhaps with just little integration of those technologies.

Transactions pertaining to loan servicing of the Maritime Employees Multi-Purpose Cooperative (MEMPCO) are being done with the use of Microsoft Excel. MEMPCO has already been existing for almost nine years now and gradually integrating ICT to provide better services

to its members and clientele. The manager and the members of the board are eager in providing their members more convenient way to access and avail various loan servicing transactions being offered by the cooperative.

The loan servicing is composed of the following transactions: inquiry of status, application of loan, and payment of amortization. Existing loan transactions involve the borrower, General Manager, Treasurer, Credit Committee Member, and the Board Member. The existing system is a bit complicated because of the manual computations and involvement of various persons.

Since the existing loan servicing system is somewhat complicated, this study was conducted to create a more convenient application in completing loan servicing transactions. Moreover, this study determined the evaluation of selected members of the cooperative on the quality of the produced software based on the ISO 9126-1 model.

The ISO 9126-1 software quality model covers six characteristics: functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability. Each characteristic is broken down further into sub-characteristics (Fahmy, et al., 2012).

Figure 1 shows the context diagram depicting the physical process model of the developed loan servicing application.

Figure 1. The physical process model of the developed application

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to produce a web-based loan servicing application for MEMPCO. Specifically, this study aimed to meet the following objectives:

- 1) develop a database using a free relational database management system;
- 2) build a web-based application for the manager and members;
- 3) produce an online application with the following features: accessing the system with appropriate credentials; viewing and updating of select member information; applying, granting, and viewing of loans; posting and viewing of payments; and generating the billing statement; and
- 4) describe the features of the developed application based on the select characteristics defined in the ISO 9126-1 software quality model.

Methodology

This study utilized the Scrum methodology for the software development and evaluation for the descriptive study.

Software Development

Sprint is considered as the heart of Scrum. It consists of Sprint Planning Meeting, Daily Scrums, the development work, the Sprint Review, and the Sprint Retrospective. Sprint is a time-box of one month or less during which a “Done”, useable, and potentially releasable product increment is created (Schwaber& Sutherland, 2011).

The software development considered a number of Sprints to produce the following increments: database design, login page, member profile, loan application, loan status, and account administration.

The development utilized XAMPP and Notepad++ as well as the following: HTML, CSS, Javascript, PHP, and MySQL. XAMPP is a free and easy to install Apache distribution containing MySQL, PHP, and Perl (Apache Friends, 2015). Notepad++ is a free source code editor and Notepad replacement that supports several languages (Ho, 2015). HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language, is a markup language for describing web documents (Refsnes Data, 2015). Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) is the language for describing the presentation of Web pages, which includes colors, layouts, and fonts (W3C, 2015). On the other hand, JavaScript, is a scripting language designed primarily for adding interactivity to Web pages and creating Web applications (JavaScripter.net, 2011). PHP, a general-purpose scripting language, is especially suited to web development (The PHP Group, 2015).

Software Evaluation

To evaluate the functionality and usability of the software, ten selected cooperative members composed of the management and officers were asked to answer the questionnaire.

Only two (2) out of the six main characteristics identified in ISO 9126-1 were covered in the evaluation: functionality and usability. The instrument contained eight (8) items and were chosen based on the characteristics that may be clearly experienced by the cooperative members who served as evaluators. Four (4) functionality sub-characteristics were included: suitability, accurateness, interoperability, and functional compliance. Also, four (4) usability sub-characteristics were included: understandability, learnability, operability, and attractiveness.

For each sub-characteristic, corresponding statement was phrased. Each statement was answerable by strongly disagree, disagree, slightly disagree, slightly agree, agree, and strongly agree with the weight of 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 6 respectively.

Mean was used to determine the evaluation on quality of the produced software as to functionality and usability. The descriptions of the quality were based on the following scale arbitrarily assigned by the researchers: “very poor” for a mean range of 1.00-2.25, “poor” for a mean range of 2.26-3.50, “good” for a mean range of 3.51-4.75, and “very good” for a mean range of 4.76-6.00.

Results and Discussion

Database Management System Used

The developed application comes with the MySQL for its database. MySQL is considered as the most popular Open Source SQL database management system developed, distributed, and supported by Oracle Corporation (Oracle Corporation, 2015).

Web-Based Application for the Manager and Members

The developed application was temporarily hosted online via web hosting account of one of the researchers. The online application only requires the participation of the borrower and the General Manager.

Features of the Developed Application

Figure 2 shows the login page of a borrower. Username and passwords are the required credentials to access the system. The same credentials are required for the general manager to login the system. The page looks the same; however, the address is different, which serves as an additional security feature.

Figure 2. Borrower's Login Page

Figure 3 shows the main page for members. Certain bits of information are displayed depending on the status. This page may be visited through the PROFILE link.

Figure 3. Member's Profile Page

Figure 4 shows the page where members may update selected information. Username, password, contact number, and address are the only data that members may immediately update. Other data that need to be updated should be channelled through the General Manager. This page may be visited through the ADMINISTRATION link.

Figure 4. Member's Administration Page

Figure 5 shows the page where a borrower applies for a loan. This may be accessed through the LOAN APPLICATION link. The borrower has to indicate the desired amount and term of payment. Upon clicking the APPLY LOAN button, verification takes place, and the application will be posted to the general manager for approval. The details of the loan application will then be reflected in the member's profile page.

Figure 5. Loan Application Page

Figure 6 shows the page where the General Manager grants the approval of a loan. If necessary, a co-maker has to be identified before the approval of loan. This page opens once a certain loan application link is clicked. Loan application link is accessible in the list of loans found through the LOANS link.

Figure 6. Loan Approval Page

Figure 7 shows the page containing the list of active loans. This page is available to the general manager and automatically displays upon the approval of a certain loan. This may also be accessed through the LOANS link. For borrowers, details of approved loan are available in their profile page.

MEMPCO Loan Administration interface showing a table of active loans. The table includes columns for Loan Number, Member No., Name, Loan Date, Amount, Terms, Per Payday, Terms Left, and Balance. A search bar is visible below the table.

Loan Number	Member No.	Name	Loan Date	Amount	Terms	Per Payday	Terms Left	Balance
30	JM-00-03121993	Barrientos, Mark Jade Dorado	Mar 30, 2015	50,000.00	10.0	2,500.00	10.0	50,000.00
8	JM-00-00004	Four, Four Four	Feb 23, 2015	45,000.00	12.0	1,875.00	6.0	22,500.00
2	JM-01-00001	One, One One	Feb 06, 2015	24,000.00	12.0	1,000.00	12.0	24,000.00
20	JM-00-00001	One Last, One First One Mid	Mar 02, 2015	15,001.00	12.0	625.04	11.5	14,375.96
345	3	Rizal, Jose	Mar 12, 2015	15,000.00	12.0	625.00	12.0	15,000.00
15-053	JM-03-0003	Three, Three Three	Mar 03, 2015	49,000.00	12.0	2,041.67	12.0	49,000.00
1	JM-02-0002	Two, Two Two	Feb 06, 2015	32,000.00	12.0	1,333.33	12.0	32,000.00
TOTAL	7 loan(s)			230,001.00				206,875.96

Search For: By: FamilyName Parameters:

Figure 7. Active Loans Page

Figure 8 shows the page where payment of a certain loan is posted. This becomes available once the loan number of an active loan is clicked. Amount, date, and official receipt number are the required data. Upon clicking the POST PAYMENT button, pertinent records shall be updated accordingly.

MEMPCO Loan Administration interface showing the payment posting form for loan 30. The form includes fields for Member Number, First Name, Middle Name, Family Name, Loan Number, Per Payday, Terms Left, Balance, Payment Amount, Payment Date, and OR No. A POST PAYMENT button is visible at the bottom.

Member Number : JM-00-03121993
 First Name : Mark Jade
 Middle Name : Dorado
 Family Name : Barrientos
 Loan Number : 30
 Per Payday : 2,500.00
 Terms Left : 10.0
 Balance : 50,000.00
 Payment Amount : 2,500.00 00,000.00
 Payment Date : 2015-03-30 yyyy-mm-dd
 OR No. :

Figure 8. Posting of Payment Page

Figure 9 shows the page containing the list of members and their corresponding payments for a chosen range of date. This page becomes available once the SELECT PAYMENTS command, under the ADMINISTRATION link, is initiated by the general manager. For borrowers, details of their payments on existing loan are available in their profile page.

Member No.	Name	Amount Paid
1	Basco, Angeline Endrina	28,750.00
1	Basco, Angeline Endrina	1,250.00
JM-00-00004	Four, Four Four	22,500.00
JM-00-0001	One Last, One First One Mid	625.04
TOTAL	4 loan(s)	53,125.04

Figure 9. List of Payments Page

Figure 10 shows the page containing the list of members with their corresponding amount due for certain due date. This page becomes available once the BILLING STATEMENT command, under the ADMINISTRATION link, has been invoked by the general manager. Due date is automatically identified based on the date that the command has been initiated. The due date is set on the 15th of the current month if the command has been initiated within the 1st to 15th of the month. Otherwise, the due date is set to the end of the current month.

Member No.	Name	Amount Due
JM-00-03121993	Barrientos, Mark Jade Dorado	2,500.00
JM-00-00004	Four, Four Four	0.00
JM-01-0001	One, One One	5,000.00
JM-00-0001	One Last, One First One Mid	1,250.08
3	Rizal, Jose	1,250.00
JM-03-0003	Three, Three Three	6,125.01
JM-02-0002	Two, Two Two	6,666.65
TOTAL	7 loan(s)	22,791.74

Figure 10. Billing Statement Page

Members' Evaluation of the Developed Application

Table 1 shows the evaluation of the selected members on the quality as to functionality and usability of the application. As to functionality, the members have evaluated the application as "very good". This is consistent to its sub-characteristics such as: suitability, accurateness, and compliance. However, its interoperability sub-characteristic was evaluated as "good" only. As to usability, the members have evaluated the application as "very good". This is constant to all its sub-characteristic, namely: understandability, learnability, operability, and attractiveness.

Table 1
Members' Evaluation of the Application

Characteristic	Mean	Description
Functionality	5.15	Very good
Suitability	4.91	Very good
Accurateness	4.82	Very good
Interoperability	4.36	Good
Compliance	5.55	Very good
Usability	5.23	Very good
Understandability	5.55	Very good
Learnability	5.27	Very good
Operability	5.27	Very good
Attractiveness	5.64	Very good

Recommendations

The utilization of MySQL as a database management system (DBMS) is a good choice for such this application. Future researchers may consider the use of this or may try other DBMS.

The produced application offers convenience and is more effective and efficient solution for loan servicing since it eliminates some people in the completion of pertinent transactions. Its use by the MEMPCO is highly recommended.

Features of the produced web application are relevant to the policies and regulations of the MEMPCO. The said application ensures accuracy in the computation of amortization and loan balance. The computation produces accurate results through a more convenient and faster way compared to the existing system. Prior to its implementation, an orientation is recommended to ensure awareness among members of the cooperative.

The "very good" evaluation on its functionality and usability shows high acceptability among evaluators; hence, it may be greatly accepted also by the other members. However, there is always room for improvement; hence, integration with the other systems may be considered in future projects.

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